
Exploring The Impact of the Relationship Between Teachers and Students on Student's Academic Performance

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ABSTRACT

In Indian society, the role of a teacher traditionally known as a “GURU”- is considered sacred and highly respected. The relationship between the teacher and students plays a crucial role in the overall learning and development of an individual. From ancient texts like Mahabharata, we see the example of Arjuna, whose success is closely connected to the guidance and mentorship of his teacher, Guru Dronacharya. This clearly shows the lasting impact a teacher can have on both the academic and personal lives of students. The present study aims at exploring how this teacher-student relationship affects student's academic performance. A strong, positive connection with the teacher can help students gain direction, confidence and motivation, all of which are essential for success. As Dr. Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan rightly stated, “A teacher is a friend, philosopher and guide,” emphasizing the multi-dimensional role teachers play in student's life. The study also aims to identify the key determinants of building and maintaining a healthy teacher-student relationship. For the purpose of this research, a descriptive survey method was used and a sample of 40 students was selected. The findings aim to highlight the value of positive teacher influence on academic performance.

Introduction

As described by the Bipolar process of Education (According to John Adam) there are two poles influencing each other. This includes – the educator means the teacher and the educand means the

student. The aim of this study is to assess the influence of the relationship between the teacher and the student or these two poles.

In a formal system of education, the place of the teacher is very crucial. The teacher is the one who establishes the bridge between the learner and education. The basic task of the teacher is to impart the knowledge to the students to learn by setting up an environment in which students can learn effectively. Teachers perform a wide range of responsibilities that differ across cultures and educational levels. In each level they do their best by following appropriate strategies and methods to make the students academically informed, cultured and to stimulate their thinking.

Since teachers spend significant time with students throughout their academic journey, it becomes their duty to cultivate a passion for learning in them. The relationship between teacher and student is a key indicator of the outcome related to the academic aspect of the students. In fact, the most effective way that a teacher can use to bring out the best in students is to build a healthy relationship with his students. It is very common that a student who perceives his teacher as more supportive has always better academic achievement. Students get motivation to learn more and more from the teacher. The influence of this teacher-student relationship is a crucial factor of student's academic achievement. For receiving quality education and achieving the academic goals, students are always influenced by the teacher. The relationship should be always positive, that there will be trust and respect for each other. It should consist of getting to know the students better, providing choices, enhancing them to become strong learners. The teacher-student bond can help the students to develop positive values and traits. The power of the connection between them is very essential to the student's academic journey. This bond also enhances the learning experience or the activities, making it more enjoyable for both teacher and students which inspires students to follow their teacher as a role model in their life. For expressing the feelings and thoughts students always want to have a comfortable response from the teacher. A positive bond between them helps the teacher to diagnose the student's needs and limitations and to take action for removing the flaws in them and improving their academic performance by guiding them through positive reinforcement and appropriate teaching strategies. As the renowned philosopher Aristotle once stated, 'Those who educate children well are more deserving to honor than parents, for they teach not just life, but how to live it well.' This highlights the powerful and lasting influence teachers have on shaping future generations.

Therefore, having a satisfactory relationship with the teacher is vital to the success of an academic career of a student. This relationship affects each and every aspect of student's academic life. The good and

positive relationship can be build or determined by various factors and this present study examines those various determinants and the overall impact of the relationship between the teacher and students on their academic performance.

Materials and Method

For carrying the present study, the investigator undertook Descriptive Survey Method. This method was used to collect data from participants in order to understand the current conditions, opinions or behaviors.

Population and Sample:

In the current study, all students of Higher Secondary level of a Senior Secondary School named Excel Senior Secondary School was taken as population. The total population was 400. A total of 40 students were chosen as the sample to fulfill the study’s objectives. One of the non-probability sampling methods i.e Random Sampling method was applied using available data believed to reflect the characteristics of the entire population. In the current study, necessary data were collected from the sample by the researcher by using a self structured questionnaire based on some previous similar studies and multiple questions were used. The author also includes certain subjective questions to analyse in details and depth.

After collecting the necessary data, the result was shown with statistical analysis which included proper graph and tables that provided detailed information.

Result

In the present study, data were collected by using a self structured questionnaire on the basis of two objectives i.e analyzing the impact of the relationship between teacher and students on student’s academic performance and to find out the determinants of building a positive relationship between teacher and students. The responses were analyzed and presented as frequencies and percentages and shown graphically.

Table 1 (Influence of teacher-student relationship on student’s academic performance)

Questions/statements	Response		Percentage	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
1. Satisfying relationship with teacher	37	3	90%	10%
2. Enjoyment of teacher’s arrival in class	39	1	96.6%	3.3%

3. Sharing problems with the teacher	27	13	55.6%	43.3%
4. Respect from teacher improves academic motivation	38	2	93.3%	6.6%
5. Constructive feedback improves grades	37	3	90%	10%
6. Teacher’s support helps in examination preparation	39	1	96.6%	3.3%
7. Encouragement from teacher improves classroom participation	40	0	100%	0
8. Comfortable communication with teacher boosts confidence	38	2	93.3%	6.6%
9. A positive relationship with teacher increases academic engagement	37	3	90%	10%
10. Interest of teacher in student’s success improves academic progress	38	2	93.3%	6.6%

Figure 1:

As seen in table 1 , a majority of the students responded positively to all the items, indicating generally a profound impact of the relationship with teacher on their overall academic performance. The highest ‘Yes’ responses were recorded for encouragement from the teacher that improves classroom participation (q.no 7) and secondly for enjoyment for teachers arrival (q.no 2) that indicates a positive results with

teacher and for teacher’s support in examination preparation (q.no 6). Notably, fewer students agreed with the item related to problem sharing with teachers (q.no 3),it may indicate lack of individual guidance or mentorship from the part of teacher because of which the students may hesitate to share their problems with them. Overall it shows a profound impact of the teacher-students relationship on the student’s academic journey or the daily performance.

Table 2 (Determinants of building a positive relationship between teacher and students)

Determinants	Yes Response	Percentage
1. Communication	34	85%
2.Mutual Respect	36	90%
3.Fair treatment	30	75%
4.Emotional support	35	87.5%
5.Encouragement	34	85%
6.Constructive feedback	35	87.5%
7.Trust	30	75%
8.Teacher’s availability outside class	32	80%
9.Positive classroom environment	30	75%
10.Student voice and expression	28	70%

Figure 2:

Table 2 shows student responses on ten key determinants contributing to positive teacher-student relationships. The highest rated factors were mutual respect (90%), emotional support (87.5%), constructive feedback (87.5%). Other consistently affirmed determinants included communication, fair treatment, encouragement, trust, teacher's availability, positive classroom environment. Lower rated but still significant was students voice and expression. Although each determinant was rated differently, their collective contribution to positive teacher-student relationships underscores the complex, multifaceted nature of academic support. The learners who feel respected, heard and valued by their teachers are always ready to engage actively in learning, which positively influences academic performance.

Discussion

The present study reveals that majority of the students viewed the relationship with their teacher as an important aspect of their academic life. As seen in table 1, 90% students responded yes about having a satisfying relationship with their teacher, and it impact their academic performance as all the students (100%) students said that encouragement they receive from their teacher improves their participation in classroom. Findings also indicate that interests of teacher in student's success improve academic progress. Teacher's support also helps the student in preparation for examination. The more students get motivated by teachers the more they improve their academic performance. A comfortable Communication between the teacher and student is another key factor that works as confidence booster to the students which enhance their learning. Here the students gets chance to express their ideas and thoughts to clear their doubts or quearies. Overall a positive relationship with teacher contributes to the increase of academic engagement. Positive reinforcement by teacher makes students excited to participate in classroom or academic activities. As the teacher guides them in the right direction, students get motivated to learn more and more. Therefore, it can be said that the teacher-student relationship has a powerful impression on the academic performance of the students. It effects many aspects of students learning. A strong supportive teacher- student relationship positively impact academic performance, with students performing better when they feel respected, understood and nurtured emotionally by the teachers.

This study also explored some determinants that contribute to the positive teacher-student relationship. From the set of ten identified determinants assessed, factors such as mutual respect, emotional support, constructive feedback and communication were highly rated which indicates that relational and emotional aspects are more valued by students. While all determinants contributed to relationship building, some such as teacher's availability outside class hours, student's voice and

expression were rated lower, suggesting that students prioritize respect and connection more. These results adhere with established research stressing the importance of emotional and interpersonal factors in academic success and highlight the need for teacher training programs to focus on only on instructional skills but also on relationship-building competencies. The teacher should be able to create an inclusive, conducive learning environment that can enhance student's learning to the optimum level.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study reinforces the pivotal role that the relationships between teacher and students play in molding academic results or educational success. The relationship between these two poles of education, i.e, the educator (teacher) and the educand (student) significantly influences student's academic journey as it effects various factors of learning such as motivation, confidence, engagement in academic activities etc. Therefore, building a positive relationship is essential for success in classroom. While various determinants contribute to positive relationship- building , students place the greatest value on relational and emotional factors. A strong, positive relationship between teachers and students can lead to improved academic performance. It is the relationship that shapes student's overall personality and academic career to live well and adjust properly to the environment. Sharing a positive relationship with the teacher promotes the maximum development in students because the teachers are the one who guide a student's life with right knowledge, a optimistic attitude and good judgement. They gave meaning to student's existence and makes them feel valued and confident. Therefore, to build a strong connection with students, the teacher should demonstrate fairness, care, respect and enthusiasm, fostering a sense of trust and mutual understading.

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